

1 **Infrequent new particle formation in a coastal Mediterranean city during the** 2 **summer**

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12

13 **Abstract**

14 Two field campaigns were conducted in Patras during the summers of 2020 and 2021 in order to
15 quantify the nucleation frequency in this area. Out of the 120 days with available measurements
16 only 15 (12%) new particle formation events occurred. This low frequency is surprising given the
17 high sunlight intensity, sulfur availability and low particle matter levels in the area during the study
18 period. On the other hand, nucleation mode particles with average diameters of 20-40 nm appeared
19 during the afternoon on 31% of the days. These particles did not grow, and the initial stages of their
20 formation could not be observed. The corresponding days are traditionally classified as undefined
21 events in similar studies. Our analysis suggests that these nucleation mode particles were not
22 associated with emissions close to the measurement site but rather they had been formed several
23 hours earlier in an area 100-150 km northeast of the field site and had grown significantly by the
24 time they reached Patras. The air mass history suggested that new particle formation often took
25 place in the vicinity of an area with significant agricultural activity and therefore high emissions of
26 ammonia and amines. The term “transported events” can be used to better characterize these
27 observed undefined days. The relatively high emissions of biogenic volatile organic compounds in
28 western Greece, where Patras is located, did not appear to assist in the local formation of new
29 particles.
30

31 **1. Introduction**

32 A significant number of new particles are introduced in the atmosphere worldwide through
33 nucleation (Kulmala et al., 2004). The resulting newly formed stable nuclei can grow to larger sizes
34 and affect climate, mostly indirectly, by increasing the total cloud condensation nuclei (CCN)

35 concentration (Spracklen et al., 2006). Nucleation and subsequent growth can account for up to half
36 of the global CCN concentrations (Gordon et al., 2017; Merikanto et al., 2009). Cloud droplets can
37 later be formed on the CCN (Kerminen et al., 2005) affecting eventually the formation, lifetime
38 and brightness of clouds. Because nucleation is a large source of ultrafine particles, it can also have
39 impacts on air quality and human health. There is evidence that elevated concentrations of ultrafine
40 particles are associated with respiratory, cardiovascular and brain (through blood flow) diseases
41 (Politis et al., 2008; Tobías et al., 2018), but also there are concerns about the ability of ultrafine
42 particles to travel directly to the brain through the olfactory nerve (Oberdörster et al., 2004).

43 The dominant mechanisms of atmospheric nucleation remain uncertain with often
44 conflicting results in the literature. It is clear that sulfuric acid plays a key role in atmospheric
45 nucleation in most environments (Kulmala and Laaksonen, 1990). However, sulfuric acid-water
46 nucleation (binary nucleation) alone cannot explain the high nucleation rates that have been
47 observed in the atmosphere (Weber et al., 1999). Additional molecules are involved in nucleation
48 at least in the lower troposphere. Ammonia or amines can help stabilize the sulfuric acid-water
49 clusters, and thus they can enhance the particle formation rate (Almeida et al., 2013; Kirkby et al.,
50 2011). Amines are better in stabilizing the clusters than ammonia, but the sparsity of measurements
51 of their relatively low concentrations often limits our ability to determine their exact role in
52 atmospheric nucleation (Kulmala et al., 2014). The ternary $\text{NH}_3 - \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ nucleation
53 mechanism has been the focus of several studies, because of ammonia's relative abundance in the
54 atmosphere (Seinfeld and Pandis, 2016). Kirkby et al. (2011) argued that the rate of this pathway
55 may also be too low to explain atmospheric observations. Other studies have argued the opposite
56 (Napari et al., 2002; Kuang et al., 2008; Kerminen et al., 2010). Organics, and especially oxidized
57 low and extremely-low volatility organic compounds can play a significant role not only in the
58 growth (along with H_2SO_4) of the newly formed particles (Kerminen et al., 2018; Riipinen et al.,
59 2011) but also in their initial formation (Lehtipalo et al., 2018). Other compounds, like iodine, can
60 also be involved in nucleation especially at coastal sites (Sellegrri et al., 2005). It is also evident that
61 nucleation can occur even in the absence of sulfuric acid from highly oxidized molecules, resulting
62 in biogenic particle formation (Kirkby et al., 2016). It is clear now that there are multiple nucleation
63 mechanisms operating in different parts of the atmosphere and different periods, which also depend
64 on the conditions and available vapor concentrations (Lee et al., 2019). However, different
65 mechanisms may dominate in different areas.

66 Although nucleation has been observed during nighttime (Hirsikko et al., 2012; Kalivitis
67 et al., 2012; Kammer et al., 2018), the intensity of solar radiation is a major factor affecting the
68 occurrence of these events worldwide (Kerminen et al., 2018); hence higher nucleation frequencies

69 are expected during the warm seasons of the year when the solar radiation is higher. Conditions
70 favorable for nucleation like lower condensation sink and higher biogenic volatile organic
71 compound emissions also tend to often be present during summer (Nieminen et al., 2014; Bousiotis
72 et al., 2021; Debevec et al., 2021). Yet, a rather surprising seasonal variation and high spatial
73 variability of the nucleation frequency during summer has been observed in Europe. Manninen et
74 al. (2010) characterized the nucleation frequency in 12 sites across Europe and found that during
75 summertime it was ranging from around 10% in Finokalia, Greece to more than 80% in Melpitz,
76 Germany. A similar variability of the nucleation frequency among various European sites was
77 reported by Patoulias et al. (2018). In the Mediterranean region, frequent events during summer
78 have been observed in San Pietro Capofiume, northern Italy, with the frequency being around 60%
79 (Hamed et al., 2007). On the other hand, in Lecce in southern Italy the nucleation frequency drops
80 to 30% (Dinoi et al., 2021). In the island of Cyprus, the probability of nucleation during
81 summertime was 40%, which, interestingly, was the seasonal minimum (Baalbaki et al., 2021). In
82 Greece, significant spatial variability of the summertime nucleation frequency has been observed,
83 varying from close to zero to up to 80%, despite the relatively small size of the country (Patoulias
84 et al., 2018). Frequent events are reported in the city of Thessaloniki in Northern Greece
85 (Siakavaras et al., 2016; Patoulias et al., 2018) while low and intermediate nucleation frequencies
86 in the range of 10-30% have been observed in Athens (Petäjä et al., 2007; Vratolis et al., 2019;
87 Kalkavouras et al., 2020) and Finokalia (Pikridas et al., 2012; Patoulias et al., 2018; Kalivitis et al.,
88 2019; Kalkavouras et al., 2020). Finally, surprisingly low nucleation frequencies have been
89 observed in the western and southern parts of the country. Kopanakis et al. (2013) reported only 2
90 nucleation events during summer in Chania, Crete while the only previous study in Patras found a
91 frequency lower than 10%, but the measurements were limited to one month (Patoulias et al., 2018).

92 To understand the reasons behind the lack of new particle formation (NPF) in Patras, Jorga
93 et al. (2023) tested the hypothesis that, despite the favorable for nucleation conditions in Western
94 Greece during summer, there is a limiting reactant whose low concentrations prevent nucleation in
95 this location. Ammonia was added in one of the two chambers of their system which had been filled
96 with ambient air. The addition of ammonia resulted in NPF in the perturbed chamber in three
97 quarters of the conducted experiments, indicating that indeed it could be the missing ingredient for
98 nucleation in this location during summertime (Jorga et al., 2023).

99 One of the key challenges in understanding the driving mechanisms of new particle
100 formation and growth is to carry out an accurate classification of the days when an event occurred.
101 NPF events are characterized by the appearance of particles with diameters close to the
102 detection limit of the corresponding measurement instrument and their gradual growth to larger

103 sizes (Kulmala et al., 2004). Dal Maso et al. (2005) proposed a simple and reliable algorithm for
104 the classification of NPF events. The method involves the visual inspection of the daily pseudo-3D
105 contour plots obtained from a scanning (SMPS) or a differential mobility particle sizer (DMPS)
106 system and is widely used. Modifications of this algorithm have been proposed, using
107 measurements of air ions and charged particles (Hirsikko et al., 2007) or their combination with
108 SMPS or DMPS data (Manninen et al., 2010). Vana et al. (2008) proposed a method for event
109 classification suitable for coastal sites. For studies at urban or suburban backgrounds, several
110 modifications have been proposed (Buenrostro Mazon et al., 2009; Németh et al., 2018) to
111 minimize biases caused by the emission of nucleation mode particles by various sources. One of
112 the limitations of these classification methods is that they involve some subjectivity and there may
113 be small variations of the classification results from researcher to researcher. To resolve this
114 problem, several automatic computer-based methods have been suggested (Joutsensaari et al.,
115 2018; Kulmala et al., 2012).

116 These algorithms classify analyzed days as; a) nucleation events, b) non-events, and c)
117 undefined, the latter being days where nucleation related particles are observed but their formation
118 and growth is ambiguous, or the event is difficult to interpret. Although a lot of attention has been
119 given to days with clear NPF events, little is known about days classified as undefined. These days
120 are often excluded from the analysis in order to reduce uncertainties in the comparison of nucleation
121 frequencies. Taking advantage of the high frequency of undefined events (40%) in the boreal forest
122 of Hyytiälä, Buenrostro Mazon et al. (2009) shed light on their characteristics and the potential
123 mechanisms affecting their occurrence. 37% of the analyzed undefined days were further classified
124 as failed events, the other categories being peaks related to emissions close to the measurement site
125 (19%), ultrafine-mode concentration peaks (34%) and unclassified days (10%). Failed events were
126 defined as periods when nucleation was evident, but either the subsequent growth or the initial
127 formation of the new particles could not be observed. These undefined days were more frequent
128 during summertime months when the frequency of clear NPF events was at its annual minimum.
129 Another study conducted in Finokalia, a remote site in the island of Crete, Greece, by Pikridas et
130 al. (2012) found that undefined days were chemically closer to nucleation events than non-events.
131 Furthermore, the campaign average condensation sink during event and undefined days was
132 comparable ($6.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $6.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively) whereas it was much higher during non-
133 events ($15.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$).

134 In this study we quantify the nucleation frequency during two consecutive summers (2020 and
135 2021) in Patras, a coastal city in Western Greece with infrequent new particle formation. An
136 emphasis is given on days traditionally classified as “undefined” to understand their origin and

137 behavior. The results are synthesized to provide insights about the dominant nucleation
138 mechanisms in Eastern Mediterranean and other similar regions.

139

140 **2. Materials and methods**

141 Continuous aerosol size distribution measurements took place in Patras, a coastal city in Western
142 Greece, during two summers (2020 and 2021) as part of the PANACEA campaigns covering most
143 of Greece. The sampling took place between 1 August and 30 September 2020 and between 15 July
144 and 15 September 2021. Data exist for a total of 120 days.

145

146 **2.1 Sampling site**

147 Patras is the third largest city of Greece with a population of around 300.000 inhabitants. The city
148 (Figure 1) is located at the foothills of mount Panachaiko, facing the gulf of Patras. The
149 measurements were conducted at the Institute of Chemical Engineering Sciences (ICE-HT), a
150 suburban background site located approximately 8 km NE from the city center (38.3° N, 21.81° E,
151 at 100 m a.s.l.). The instruments were located inside an air-conditioned room (20 °C) and were
152 sampling from approximately 5 m above ground. The nearby area is characterized by low
153 vegetation and olive trees while the sea is about 2 km to the north. Notable nearby sources include
154 the Patras-Athens highway (1 km away), a cement plant (6 km away) and the port of Patras is
155 located 11 km southwest from the sampling site.

156

157 **2.2 Instrumentation**

158 The particle number size distributions were measured using one or two scanning mobility particle
159 sizers (SMPS, TSI inc.) with a time resolution of 4 min. For the measurement of the particles in the
160 range of 14 – 750 nm the system consisted of a classifier (model 3080, TSI), a water CPC (model
161 3787, TSI) and a DMA (model 3081, TSI). The sample flow rate was 1.5 L min⁻¹ and the sheath
162 flow was set to 3 L min⁻¹. A second SMPS (classifier model 3080, CPC model 3775, DMA model
163 3085, TSI) was used in Patras during the campaign of 2021 for the measurement of the particles in
164 the range of 4-14 nm. The sample flow was 1.5 L min⁻¹ and the sheath flow was set at 15 L min⁻¹.
165 The sampling lines of the two SMPS systems were one quarter inch copper tubes with a length of
166 2 m. The particles were sampled without drying.

167 During the summer 2021 campaign, a nano Condensation Nucleus Counter system (model
168 A11 nCNC, Airmodus) was also deployed, providing information regarding nanoparticles with
169 diameters in the range of 1-4 nm. The sample flow was 2.5 L min⁻¹ and the system consisted of a

170 particle size magnifier (PSM, model A10, Airmodus) used for the growth of the smallest particles
171 with diethylene glycol (DEG) and a butanol CPC (model A20, Airmodus) for the measurement of
172 their number concentration. The sampling line of the PSM was a quarter inch copper tube 0.5 m
173 long. The PSM data were inverted according to the methods provided by Cai et al. (2018).

174 A Multi-Angle Absorption Photometer (MAAP model 5012, Thermo Scientific) and an
175 Aethalometer (model A33, Magee Scientific) were deployed for the measurement of black carbon
176 and monitors for the measurement of SO₂ (model 43i-TLE, Thermo Scientific), NO_x, NH₃ (model
177 T201, Teledyne) and O₃ (model 400E, Teledyne) concentrations were used. Also, a Purple Air low-
178 cost sensor (model PA-II) was available for measurements of the PM_{2.5} mass concentration. The
179 corresponding low cost-sensor data were corrected following Kosmopoulos et al. (2022).
180 Measurements of various meteorological parameters included temperature, relative humidity, wind
181 direction, precipitation, and solar radiation.

182

183 **3. Data analysis**

184 **3.1 Event classification**

185 For the event classification we used the algorithm proposed by Dal Maso et al. (2005). Initially, the
186 3-D pseudo contour plots were constructed and inspected for each day of the summer 2020 and
187 2021 campaigns in order to be classified. The method takes into consideration several
188 characteristics of the newly formed particles like their size (< 25 nm), their temporal evolution, and
189 growth. The days when an NPF event was observed were further classified into Class I, if the event
190 was clear and the particle formation and growth rates could be easily estimated, and Class II if
191 fluctuations in particle concentration and diameter were observed in the nucleation mode particles.
192 Days that were classified as “undefined” involved the sudden appearance of nucleation mode
193 particles that persisted for more than one hour but did not grow sufficiently or their initial formation
194 was not observed (even if they exhibited some growth) in order to be considered NPF events.
195 Finally, because the measurements were conducted in a suburban location, during each potential
196 event, other available measurements (BC, SO₂ and NO_x) were inspected to verify that the observed
197 particles were not emitted by nearby combustion sources. Days when nucleation mode particles
198 were observed at the same time with correlated increases in concentrations of black carbon or NO_x
199 or SO₂, were classified as non-events.

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204 **3.2 Air mass origin analysis**

205 For the investigation of the air mass origin, the 24-h backward air trajectories arriving at the ICE-
206 HT station during the two summer campaigns were calculated using the Hybrid Single-Particle
207 Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory (HYSPLIT_4) model developed by the NOAA Air Resource
208 Laboratory (Draxler and Hess, 1998). The default arrival height chosen for the analysis was 50 m
209 above ground level but trajectories arriving at 1000 m were also inspected. One trajectory was
210 estimated for each hour (24 trajectories per day). For both summers, the Global Forecast System
211 (GFS 0.25 degrees, NOAA) meteorological files were used. The Weather Research and Forecasting
212 (WRF) model (Skamarock et al., 2008) was used for the calculation of the meteorological fields
213 that are required as input by HYSPLIT for the summer of 2021. WRF was used with a 4 km grid
214 resolution for Greece that was nested into a 12 km grid for the rest of Europe. The calculated
215 trajectory endpoints were further analyzed using the Openair package (Carslaw and Ropkins,
216 2012).

217

218 **4. Results and discussion**

219 **4.1 Atmospheric conditions during the two campaigns**

220 During both campaigns the average temperature was approximately 27 °C, varying from 17 to 35
221 °C during the summer of 2020 and from 18 to 40 °C during the summer of 2021. The summer of
222 2021 was characterized by some periods with high temperatures due to a heatwave that peaked at
223 the beginning of August (Founda et al., 2022). The average relative humidity was a little higher
224 during the 2020 summer campaign (58%) than the 2021 campaign (51%) and ranged between 10-
225 100% and 10 – 85%, respectively. Solar radiation was higher than 750 W m⁻² at noon, during most
226 days (>80%) and the rain events were rare and short lived (4 rain events in 120 days). The average
227 diurnal profiles of the meteorological parameters for both measurement periods can be found in the
228 Supplement (Fig. S1).

229 The atmosphere of Patras was relatively clean during both periods. The average PM_{2.5}
230 concentrations were 6±2.9 µg m⁻³ and 7±4.3 µg m⁻³, while the particle number (N_{14}) varied between
231 800 – 12000 cm⁻³ and had a mean value of 3370 ± 1300 cm⁻³ and 3490 ± 2250 cm⁻³ during the
232 summer 2020 and 2021 campaigns, respectively. The Aitken mode (25 – 100 nm) accounted for
233 around 46% and 50% of the N_{14} , while the accumulation mode (100 – 750 nm) accounted for around
234 49% and 39% during the summers of 2020 and 2021, respectively. The nucleation mode (<25 nm)
235 particles accounted for only 5% of the N_{14} during the 2020 period, whereas the corresponding

236 fraction for summer 2021 was 11%. Considering the measurements down to 1 nm (available for
237 summer 2021), the nucleation mode particles (1.3 – 25 nm) accounted for 15% of the $N_{1.3}$.

238 The levels of various pollutants were comparable between the two campaigns; NO_x
239 concentration was 3.3 ± 2 ppb, SO_2 was 0.5 ± 0.3 ppb, BC was $0.5 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. Ozone measurements
240 were available only during the 2021 summer campaign and was on average 41 ± 12 ppb. Average
241 diurnal variations of the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and the various pollutants concentrations are available in the
242 Supplement for the summer of 2020 (Fig. S2) and the summer of 2021 (Fig. S3). A morning peak
243 was observed in the NO_x and BC concentrations at around 9:00 LT, reaching values of 4 ppb and
244 $0.6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ respectively, and also a smaller one during late afternoon (19:30 LT). These peaks can
245 be attributed to the morning and afternoon rush hours. Sulfur dioxide is characterized by a small
246 increase of 0.1-0.2 ppb at 9:00 LT that lasted until the end of the day. Finally, ozone increased by
247 10 ppb on average during daytime, peaking at around 15:00 LT.

248

249 **4.2 NPF events in Patras during summer**

250 The available size distribution measurements had a total data coverage of 97%. Typical examples
251 of each different category are depicted in Figure 2 along with their corresponding particle number
252 (N_{14} or $N_{1.3}$) concentrations. The Class I event in Patras during 27/09/20 shows the appearance and
253 continuous growth of new particles in the smallest size bins of the SMPS after 13:00 LT (Fig. 2a),
254 while the Class II event during 09/09/21 is again characterized by the appearance of small new
255 particles at 11:00 LT, but their growth is not continuous (Fig. 2b). Overall, Class I events were
256 characterized by the continuous evolution of particle number and the size distribution. During Class
257 II events, although new particle formation and growth was observed, the temporal evolution of the
258 size distribution or the number concentration did not exhibit a clear pattern. In the undefined event
259 shown in Fig. 2c, new particles appeared at around 11:00 LT, but their formation and growth was
260 not observed. Finally, Fig. 2d shows a day where no nucleation was observed.

261 The nucleation frequency was calculated taking into account both the Class I and Class II
262 events and dividing their number by the total number of days. Out of the 120 days, there were only
263 3 Class I events (2%) and 12 Class II events (10%), confirming the surprising low nucleation
264 frequency in Southern Greece (Patoulas et al., 2018; Vratolis et al., 2019). The detailed event
265 statistics (Table 1) suggest that the nucleation frequency was similar in both summers (15% during
266 summer of 2020 and 10% during summer of 2021) with an average of 12%, while numerous
267 undefined days were observed during both campaigns. Because the measurements took place at
268 ground level, it is also possible that there are some events that take place above the boundary

269 layer (about 1-2 km during noon in Patras during summer) and are not observed at the
270 ground.

271

272 **4.2.1 Characteristics of the nucleation events**

273 The 15 observed NPF events were further analyzed to investigate their characteristics and the
274 potential mechanisms involved. For the summer of 2020 information about particles smaller than
275 14 nm was not available, thus the exact initiation time was difficult to determine. Nucleation events
276 typically started between 11:00 – 13:00 LT, and their duration varied between 4 – 7 h. The growth
277 rates (GR_{14-25}) of the three Class I events were estimated using the maximum-concentration method
278 (Kulmala et al., 2012) and were equal to 6.5, 5.7 and 9.2 nm h⁻¹ respectively. The N_{14} during the
279 nucleation events increased by 10³ – 10⁴ cm⁻³ and the maximum diameter of the newly formed
280 particles was 70-80 nm.

281 The condensation sink (CS) is a useful parameter for the analysis because high CS values
282 can often limit NPF. The CS was estimated using the available SMPS data according to:

$$CS = 2\pi D \sum_i \beta_i d_{pi} N_i \quad (1)$$

283 where D is the diffusion coefficient of the condensable vapors, β_i the transition regime correction
284 factor (Sutugin and Fuchs, 1970), d_{pi} the diameter of a SMPS size-channel i and N_i the number
285 concentration of that specific size-channel. In this study, the diffusion coefficient of H₂SO₄ and a
286 mean free path of 123 nm for the calculation of β_i were used (Dinoi et al., 2021; Erupe et al., 2010).
287 High levels of preexisting particles in the atmosphere result in a larger surface area, increasing the
288 CS. The average CS (Fig. 3a), calculated for the period of 8:00 – 20:00 LT was $6.3 \pm 5.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$
289 during Class I and II events and $9.6 \pm 4.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ during non-events and their difference was
290 statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). This indicates that nucleation occurred during relatively cleaner
291 days. Lower values of the CS seem to favor nucleation in Greece as in most areas (Pikridas et al.,
292 2012; Kalivitis et al., 2019; Kalkavouras et al., 2020).

293 Between nucleation events (Class I and II) and non-events, there was not a clear difference
294 in relative humidity (Fig. 3b). A higher wind speed (Fig. 3c) was observed during nucleation events,
295 being 2.8 m s⁻¹ (and 2.2 m s⁻¹ for the non-events). Since SO₂ when oxidized (into H₂SO₄), is one of
296 the most important ingredients for the formation of new particles, its levels were compared (Fig.
297 3d) for the nucleation event and non-event days as well. There was not a significant difference of
298 the mean SO₂ concentration between the two cases, being 0.41±0.26 ppb for the Class I and II
299 events and 0.42±0.27 ppb for the non-events. Nevertheless, these concentrations of SO₂ imply that

300 there were sufficient amounts of H₂SO₄ for nucleation considering the high OH levels (of the order
301 of 10⁷ molecule cm⁻³) in coastal Greece during the summer.

302 Figure 4 depicts the 24h-backward air trajectories for a) the non-event days and b) the NPF
303 (Class I and II) days during both campaigns, arriving in the 8:00-22:00 LT period. For the NPF
304 events, the trajectories correspond to the particular hours during which the particles were observed
305 in Patras. During 53% of the nucleation events, the air was coming from the west while for the rest
306 it was coming from the northeast of Patras. Although there was not a clear association of the wind
307 direction with NPF events, the length of the trajectories during these days implies higher wind
308 speeds of the airmasses compared to the non-events. The air masses from the west passed over the
309 Ionian Sea for several hours but about 1-6 h prior to arriving at Patras, they usually traveled over
310 land in the northwest or the southwest of Patras. These locations are characterized by various
311 agricultural activities; hence elevated ammonia levels are expected in these air masses which can
312 in turn induce nucleation. For example, the two most intense Class I events of the campaigns
313 (27/9/2020 and 27/8/2021) were accompanied by air masses that passed over the agricultural areas
314 in Ilia in the southwest of Patras. The corresponding air masses (Fig. S4) traveled over the Ionian
315 Sea for several hours, but around 2-4 h before arriving at Patras, they travelled over the main
316 agricultural area in western Peloponnese. Air masses that arrived at the Patras site directly from the
317 sea (without spending several hours over land) were not associated with NPF. The marine air
318 masses in these cases can still be enriched with amines but these compounds may be rapidly
319 transferred to the particulate phase, or they may lack other compounds necessary for the formation
320 and growth of the stable nuclei (for example sulfuric acid or organics). Similar observations have
321 been reported by Zhu et al. (2019) in the marine atmosphere, where all but one NPF events were
322 connected with transport of various pollutants from continental areas.

323

324 **4.3 Analysis of the undefined events**

325 The surprisingly frequent undefined days (>30%) in Patras during summer were further analyzed
326 in detail to investigate the source of the already grown nucleation mode particles, and to explain
327 their lack of growth to larger sizes. In these cases, the initial particle formation could not be detected
328 by neither the PSM nor the nano SMPS. There was also a case on Aug. 24, 2021 (Fig. S5) where
329 the nucleation mode particles exhibited signs of growth, but their initial formation again could not
330 be observed in the sub-10 nm channels.

331 All 37 undefined days were characterized by the appearance of a new particle mode in the
332 diameter range between 15 – 30 nm (Figure 5), while in all cases these particles were detected at
333 the site during 12:00 – 17:00 and were present for 5 – 8 hours (Figure 6). During both 2020 and

334 2021, the mean mode diameter was 23 ± 5 nm. In the summer of 2021 particles appearing during
335 morning and midday exhibited a limited growth until 15:00 while a decrease was observed in their
336 mean diameter during the late afternoon hours. Significant decrease in the mode diameter (up to 10
337 nm) was observed in 9 out of the 37 days. Apparent decrease in the mode diameter of the newly
338 formed particles has been observed also in other environments (Hakala et al., 2019; Salma et al.,
339 2016) and appears to be due to the more limited growth during transport, given that the
340 photochemistry is slowing down during the afternoon. Another potential explanation of this
341 decrease in particle size is that during periods of higher temperatures these particles may be
342 partially evaporating.

343 The average condensation sink during undefined days was $8.1 \pm 2.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and was higher
344 than during the events (Class I and II) but still lower than the corresponding average for non-events
345 (Fig 3a). There was a notable difference in the RH between undefined and non-event days, being
346 on average $45 \pm 15\%$ and $56 \pm 16\%$ respectively. The undefined days were also characterized by
347 higher wind speeds (Fig. 3c) than the rest of the days. Overall, the SO_2 levels during undefined
348 days were higher than both the nucleation and non-event days, being on average 0.5 ± 0.24 ,
349 0.41 ± 0.26 ppb and 0.42 ± 0.27 ppb respectively. The aforementioned differences were statistically
350 significant ($\alpha = 0.01$) and were attributed to the particular origin of the air masses during undefined
351 events, analyzed in the next section.

352 In an effort to identify the origin of these particles, the hypothesis that they were due to
353 nearby emission sources was tested. Primary emissions usually affect the whole size distribution
354 and not only the nucleation-mode. The levels of BC, NO_x and SO_2 were also inspected during the
355 periods that these particle modes were observed. These nucleation modes during undefined days
356 were accompanied by elevated concentrations of BC, or NO_x or SO_2 only on 2 out of the 37 days
357 (5%). This suggests that these small particles were not a result of nearby emission sources in the
358 greater area of the measurement site, during 95% of the days. For example, during July 27, 2021
359 (Figure 7), while a new mode of particles in the range of 20-30 nm appeared at around 11:30 LT,
360 the concentrations of SO_2 , NO_x and BC did not exhibit any significant changes at the period
361 between 11:30 and 18:30. Sulfur dioxide increased at 11:30 by almost 0.4 ppb, while no changes
362 were observed in the concentrations of NO_x and BC. The concentration of SO_2 returned to its initial
363 levels after 2 h while the mode persisted for more than 8 h. A possible explanation of these small
364 concentration increases could be that different air masses arrived at that time in Patras containing
365 higher concentrations of SO_2 and also these already grown new particles. On the other hand, the
366 particles appearing at around 21:00 on the same day, are associated with nearby emission sources,

367 given the fact that elevated concentrations of SO₂, NO_x and BC are observed during the same time
368 period (Fig. 7).

369

370 **4.3.1 Air mass origin**

371 The next step was to test the hypothesis that the observed nucleation mode particles were
372 transported to the site. First, we analyzed the local meteorology, focusing on the wind direction and
373 speed (Fig. S6) for a) the entire period, b) the undefined and c) the non-event days of each
374 campaign. During the 2020 and 2021 campaigns the prevailing local wind direction was either from
375 the southwest (220° - 270°) or from the east – northeast (30° - 100°) of Patras. When comparing
376 the wind direction during undefined and non-event days, a clear difference during both campaigns
377 was observed. During non-events, southwestern winds were dominant. On the other hand, the
378 sudden appearance of already grown particles (undefined days) was accompanied by mainly eastern
379 (summer 2020) and north-eastern winds (summer 2021) coming mainly from central Greece.

380 Because the greater area of Patras is quite mountainous (Figure 1), the analysis of the local
381 meteorology is not sufficient to identify the origin of the new mode particles during undefined days.
382 24-h backward air trajectories were calculated for every hour of each day during both campaigns.
383 Those that arrived in Patras at the period between 8:00 and 22:00 LT during non-event and
384 undefined days were compared. We focused on this period because nucleation is usually photo-
385 induced, and particles associated with it are formed and transferred mostly during daytime.

386 Figures 4c and 4d show the comparison between the trajectories during days and hours that
387 these particles were and were not observed during the two summers. Overall, the air masses had
388 approximately the same probability of passing over the north-eastern as well as the north-western
389 regions of Greece. A completely different behavior was observed during the undefined days and
390 hours. Practically all the trajectories (90%) were coming from the north-eastern direction (Fig. 4d).
391 This was also consistent with the behavior of the corresponding trajectories arriving at 1000 m
392 above ground level (Fig. S7). In Patras there were only 6 exceptions out of the 37 undefined days
393 when the air masses were coming from either the NW or the SW. The existence of these days
394 suggests that there must be also other areas where nucleation occur (with a lower frequency), and
395 the grown particles are then transported to Patras. The strong connection of the majority of the
396 undefined days with air masses from the northeast, together with the behavior and appearance times
397 of the observed nucleation modes, support the hypothesis that these particles are the result of
398 nucleation in another area and subsequent growth during the few hours of their transport to the
399 measurement site. Hence, these undefined days from now on can be reclassified as “transported

400 events”. This term was also used by Dada et al. (2018) to describe similar cases that were frequently
401 observed in the boreal forest of Hyytiälä, Finland.

402

403 **4.4 Potential area of nucleation during undefined events**

404 The potential area of nucleation during the transported events observed in Patras can be estimated
405 considering a) the predominant pathways of the air masses arriving at these specific hours and b)
406 the time required for the newly formed clusters to grow to sizes of about 20-30 nm. Typical growth
407 rates in Greece during summer vary from 2 to up to 10 nm h⁻¹ (Kalivitis et al., 2019; Kalkavouras
408 et al., 2020; Kopanakis et al., 2013; Pikridas et al., 2012; Siakavaras et al., 2016). The rare “Class
409 I” events observed in Patras had a growth rate of about 6 nm h⁻¹ (two out of three events), hence an
410 average GR of 6 nm h⁻¹ was assumed. With that assumption, these particles would need around 4.2
411 ± 1.2 h to grow to the observed diameters. For this analysis we focused on 6-h backward trajectories
412 to gain a more detailed perspective about the potential locations of nucleation. The mean arrival
413 time of these particles was at around 15:00, and given the fact that nucleation occurs mostly during
414 high sunlight hours, these could not have been formed much earlier than 6 h. We implicitly assume
415 here that these particles were not the result of nucleation that occurred during the previous day. The
416 fact that these particles never arrived during the night supports this hypothesis.

417 The comparison of the trajectories between undefined and non-event days was made
418 calculating the potential source contribution function (PSCF):

$$PSCF = \frac{m_{ij}}{n_{ij}} \quad (2)$$

419 where for a given grid cell with geographic coordinates (i,j), m_{ij} is the number of times that the
420 trajectories passed over the cell during undefined hours in Patras and n_{ij} is the total number times
421 that the trajectories passed over this cell during the entire period (Pekney et al., 2006). PSCF is
422 traditionally used for the identification of nearby or distant locations that are responsible for
423 elevated concentrations of various pollutants (SO₂, PM_{2.5}, BC etc.) detected in a measurement site
424 after their transport there. The PSCF value expresses the conditional probability that the higher than
425 an arbitrarily defined threshold (for example above the 90th percentile) concentrations of a given
426 species, are associated with air masses coming from a specific location. The higher the PSCF value
427 over a grid cell, the higher the probability the corresponding air masses that pass over that cell to
428 be enriched in high concentrations of the studied pollutant.

429 In our analysis, we treat each undefined day/hour as the same, regardless of the increase of
430 the N_{14} (or $N_{1.3}$ when available). Thus, the PSCF values were calculated considering as “elevated
431 concentrations” all the periods that these particles were appearing in Patras. Figure 8 illustrates the

432 potential NPF related PSCF values. The PSCF values were elevated in a region ~100 km NE of the
433 sampling site. The PSCF reached its maximum value (almost 50%) over a large agricultural area
434 with a surface area of around 300 km². High PSCF values on the grid cells right next and east of
435 Patras, can be attributed to the fact that the already enriched with new particles trajectories had
436 followed the same route to get to the site so they were also present in these grid cells. Besides, if
437 nucleation had occurred in this area which is above the gulf of Corinth, the particles would not have
438 enough time to grow to sizes larger than 20 nm. Considering all the above observations, and with
439 an assumed GR of 6 nm h⁻¹, the estimated potential area of nucleation is depicted with a dashed
440 circle in Fig. 8.

441

442 **4.5 Ammonia and biogenic emissions over Greece during summer**

443 The emissions of gas phase ammonia over Greece were estimated for a summer period (August
444 2017) using the TNO inventory (Kuenen et al., 2014). Biogenic emissions were estimated by the
445 Model of Emissions of Gases and Aerosols from Nature (MEGAN) (Guenther et al., 2006). Since
446 both NH₃ and biogenic VOCs are emitted from sources that exhibit small changes with time, we
447 expect that the differences in the spatial distribution of these emissions between 2017 and 2020 and
448 2021 to be minor.

449 Ammonia emissions (Fig. 9a) are higher in the central parts of the country compared to the
450 western and southern areas. These are the largest agricultural areas of Greece (Gemtzi et al., 2019).
451 The Iliia area southwest of Patras where ammonia levels are also elevated can also be seen in Fig.
452 9a. The potential area of nucleation estimated for the vast majority (90%) of the air trajectories
453 during the transported events (coming from the northeast) is one of the main agricultural areas of
454 the country. Nucleation and subsequent growth could be frequent in that location due to increased
455 levels of ammonia that are expected there. Also, during the few remaining undefined days, when
456 the air was coming from NW or SW, it again spent some time over land areas with elevated
457 ammonia emissions before arriving at Patras, indicating that nucleation in a limited spatial extent
458 may be happening (with a smaller frequency) in these areas as well.

459 On the other hand, biogenic emissions (Fig. 9b) tend to be higher in the western part of the
460 country where several forests exist (Gemtzi et al., 2019). The average midday concentration of the
461 monoterpenes in Patras is 0.5 ppb and of isoprene equal to 1.5 ppb (Kaltsonoudis et al., 2016).
462 These concentrations are comparable to the levels in which biogenic volatile organic compounds
463 are expected to participate in the formation and growth of new particles. Therefore, when
464 nucleation and subsequent growth occurs in Patras, organics probably play a role in the growth of

465 the newly formed particles. However, it is clear from our measurements that frequent NPF events
466 dominated by biogenic volatile organics are not taking place in Patras.

467 The relatively high emissions of biogenic volatile organic compounds in western Greece
468 did not appear to assist in the local formation of new particles. The low ammonia emissions in the
469 greater area of Patras combined with the fact that its atmospheric transportation from other areas is
470 limited due to its relatively small residence time (Asman et al., 1998), can explain the surprisingly
471 low nucleation frequency observed during summer in this location. Another possible reason of the
472 infrequent NPF could be its suppression due to high levels of isoprene (Fig. S8) compared to
473 monoterpenes (Kiendler-Scharr et al., 2009; Kanawade et al., 2011; Lee et al., 2016).

474

475 **5. Conclusions**

476 Field campaigns were conducted during two consecutive summers (2020 and 2021) at a coastal city
477 in Western Greece, to quantify the nucleation frequency and investigate the reasons behind the
478 infrequent new particle formation observed in this area. A total of 120 days' worth of measurements
479 were analyzed.

480 A surprisingly low nucleation frequency (on average 12%) was observed in Patras during
481 both campaigns. There were only 3 clear Class I events (2%) while the class II events were 12
482 (10%). The corresponding days of the events (both Class I and II) were characterized by lower CS
483 values and higher wind speed compared to the non-event days. There was not a significant
484 difference in relative humidity. The 3 clear nucleation events had growth rates equal to 6.5, 5.7 and
485 9.2 nm h⁻¹ and the produced N₁₄ were in the range of 10³-10⁴ cm⁻³. Although the observed nucleation
486 events (Class I and II) were not associated with any particular wind direction, the two strongest
487 events of both campaigns occurred when the air masses were passing over an agricultural region to
488 the south of Patras.

489 Contrary to the nucleation frequency, a high frequency (31%) of undefined events was
490 observed in Patras. During these days, new modes of small particles in the range of 20-40 nm
491 appeared during early afternoon and persisted for 5-8 h. Lower CS and RH and higher wind speed
492 characterized these days comparing to the non-events. In 95% of the cases the nucleation modes
493 were not accompanied by significant increases in the concentration of SO₂, NO_x or BC, suggesting
494 that they were not originating from emission sources close to the field site.

495 The analysis of air mass origin during the days and specific hours of appearance of these
496 small particle modes, suggests that they were transported mainly (90%) from regions to the
497 northeast of Patras. The term "transported events" was introduced to describe these undefined days
498 observed in Patras. Using the expected growth rates, the formation of these particles was estimated

499 to take place in a major agricultural region approximately 100 km NE of Patras, where ammonia
500 emissions are elevated. On the other hand, lack of local ammonia emissions in Patras could explain
501 the low nucleation frequency, despite the favorable conditions for NPF in the area during summer.
502 The moderate biogenic volatile organic compound levels in Patras do not appear to assist in the
503 local NPF.

504

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515 maps from the PMCAMx model and SNP was responsible for the design of the study, the synthesis
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517

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Table 1. Event statistics during the 2020 and 2021 campaign.

Day classification	Summer 2020		Summer 2021	
	Number of days	Percentage (All days)	Number of days	Percentage (All days)
Class I	1	2	2	3
Class II	8	13	4	7
Undefined	18	30	19	32
Non-event	33	55	35	58
Total days	60		60	

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Figure 1. Elevation map of Greece indicating the measurement site in Patras.

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Figure 2. Typical examples of a) Class I, b) Class II, c) Undefined and d) Non-event particle number size distributions. The corresponding N_{14} or N_1 during each day is also shown.

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841 **Figure 3.** Comparison of the average a) CS, b) RH, c) wind speed and d) SO₂ values during
842 nucleation event, non-event, and undefined days, calculated for the time period 8:00 – 20:00 LT.
843 The red lines represent the median while the box edges the 25th and 75th percentiles. The whiskers
844 correspond to the 10th and 90th percentiles. The number of days in each category is also shown at
845 the top.

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849 **Figure 4.** The 24-h backward air trajectories arriving at Patras during both campaigns in 2020 and
 850 2021 for: a) non-events (1696 trajectories); b) nucleation (Class I and II) events (90 trajectories);
 851 c) non-undefined (1532 trajectories); and d) undefined (transported) events (254 trajectories). The
 852 trajectories shown for the nucleation and undefined events (red and green) correspond only to the
 853 hours during which the particles appeared in Patras during each event. On the other hand, the
 854 trajectories for the rest of the days (blue) correspond to the hours between 8:00-22:00 LT.

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858 **Figure 5.** Variation of the mean diameter of the new-mode particles observed during undefined
859 days for summer a) 2020 and b) 2021. The box edges represent the 25th and 75th percentile while
860 the whiskers the 10th and 90th percentile. The red lines correspond to the median and the blue dots
861 are the mean.

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867 **Figure 6.** The temporal distribution of the mode observation frequency for the summer campaigns
868 of: a) 2020 and b) 2021.

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870 **Figure 7.** A particle number size distribution during an undefined day (27/07/2021) together with
 871 the b) SO₂, c) NO_x (NO₂ shown with blue and NO with green lines) and d) BC concentrations
 872 during the same day. The dashed lines represent the beginning and the ending of the undefined
 873 event.

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879 **Figure 8.** The PSCF values, calculated for both the 2020 and 2021 campaigns. Only the 6-h
880 trajectories that correspond to the particular hours during which the particles appeared in Patras
881 during an undefined day (transported event) were included in the PSCF calculation.

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883 **Figure 9.** Emissions for 36x36 km computational cells of: a) ammonia and b) monoterpenes during
884 August 2017.